

A Neutron Balance Method for Low-Cost Prediction of Scalar Neutron Flux Spectra after Cross Section Perturbation

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ABSTRACT

This work introduces a new method called Perturbed Spectrum Prediction (PSP) for estimating how multi-group scalar flux distributions in steady-state neutron transport problems change energetically and spatially in response to a perturbation in the macroscopic reaction cross sections. This method uses a simplified region-averaged neutron balance approach to relate changes in cross sections to changes in the scalar flux. In contrast to other existing methods, PSP requires only a single initial many-group transport solution with no other significant initial computation. PSP is able to be implemented with standard neutral particle transport solvers, and is generalizable to many different types of systems. This allows one to much more quickly estimate changes in fine spectral features without the computational expense of an additional many-group transport calculation. The cost of each prediction lies in constructing a relatively-small coefficient matrix and performing an SVD. The derivation of this method from the NTE is outlined and all major assumptions/approximations are noted. The method is demonstrated using PARTISN as a reference transport solver. A series of tests are performed on 1-D and 2-D problems with varying geometries and spectral characteristics. These tests yield promising results. In some cases, an $\sim 11x$ reduction in reaction rate prediction error was observed when compared to using the unperturbed flux spectrum. Future work will focus on evaluating the method for specific applications.

Keywords: neutron transport, multigroup, scalar flux, cross sections, perturbation

1. INTRODUCTION

In neutronic analysis, knowledge of the finely-resolved energy characteristics of the scalar neutron flux is important to making accurate predictions of system behavior. Because neutron interaction cross sections change rapidly with respect to neutron energy a finely-detailed understanding of spectral characteristics is needed to accurately predict quantities of interest, such as local reaction rate densities and heat generation densities. With multigroup methods, the resolution of the information we can gain about the flux spectrum is dictated by the resolution of the group structure used to discretize the energy domain. Finely-resolved spectral information therefore requires group structures with many finely-resolved energy groups. For multigroup transport calculations with G -many energy groups, the computational cost typically scales $O(G)$ and the memory requirements typically scale $O(G^2)$. Hence, it quickly becomes very computationally-expensive to use a finely-discretized energy domain.

Here we analyze a set of steady-state cases which have the same geometry but differ in their macroscopic reaction cross sections. These types of problems often arise when looking at a system which slowly evolves isotopically or thermally over time, such as in a reactor burnup calculation [1]. If we choose one of these cases to be the 'base', we can consider the remaining cases to be perturbed about this base case. Repeatedly solving high-fidelity many-group transport problems for each of these cases is often prohibitively computationally-expensive. The open question is therefore how should one go

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about efficiently estimating the fine spectral characteristics in each of these cases. In essence, the question becomes how can one estimate the spatially-dependent fine-group scalar flux spectra in each of these perturbed cases without solving a fine-group transport problem for each case.

Many methods of doing this already exist. A problem like this naturally lends itself to the adjoint-based perturbation theory methods commonly used in reactor analysis. Although adjoint-based methods are typically used to estimate changes in whole-system integral parameters such as reactivity, it has been shown that one can accurately predict group-wise scalar fluxes using a high-order modal expansion method [2]. The downside with this method is the high initial computational cost to perform the two many-group transport calculations on the base case, one forward and one adjoint, and to construct the modal expansion. Another method of interest comes from generalized energy condensation theory in which a solution that mimics the spectral properties of a many-group transport solution can be found within an inexpensive modified few-group framework [3]. However, this method lies outside of the typical multigroup approximation and solvers for the requisite modified few-group problems have yet to be implemented in industry-standard neutron transport codes. Other application-specific methods have been developed [4], but they are often significantly limited in their scope, relying on strong assumptions about the energy group structure and material composition of the problem of interest.

Towards the goal of creating a low-cost generalizable method that can be implemented with industry standard tools, a neutron balance-based approach called Perturbed Spectrum Prediction (PSP) has been developed. In this PSP method, the flux solution from a single many-group forward transport calculation is used to construct a linear system of neutron balance equations. Solving this system yields a prediction of the ratio between the perturbed and base group-wise scalar fluxes. This system is solved approximately, not analytically, because the linear system is generally ill-posed. The prediction of the perturbed scalar flux is then constructed from these flux ratios and the existing base scalar flux solution. In constructing the linear system, this method makes assumptions about the similarity of the spatial distributions of the scalar flux between the base and perturbed problems as well as assuming optical thickness in the spatial regions. These assumptions may not be accurate for all types of problems, but PSP has shown promising results when applied to a series of simple 1-D and 2-D test problems.

2. THEORY AND METHODS

2.1. Multigroup Neutron Balance and The Flux Ratio Equation

First, we will derive the flux ratio equation that relates the changes in the reaction cross sections to the changes in the scalar fluxes. We can begin with the k -eigenvalue form of the continuous-energy NTE:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \psi(x, \hat{\Omega}, E) + \Sigma_t(x, E) \psi(x, \hat{\Omega}, E) &= \int_0^\infty \int_{4\pi} \Sigma_s(x, \hat{\Omega}' \cdot \hat{\Omega}, E' \rightarrow E) \psi(x, \hat{\Omega}', E') d\Omega' dE' \\ &+ \frac{\chi(x, E)}{4\pi k} \int_0^\infty \int_{4\pi} \nu \Sigma_f(x, E') \psi(x, \hat{\Omega}', E') d\Omega' dE', \\ x \in V, \hat{\Omega} \in 4\pi, 0 < E < \infty \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

If we integrate both sides of the equation over all directions, integrate over a given spatial region R , and apply the multigroup approximation in energy, we can write out the multigroup balance equation for the region R and energy group G as shown in Equation 2.

$$\iiint_R \Sigma_{t,G}(x) \phi_G(x) dV = J_{net,G} + \iiint_R \sum_{G'=1}^{N_G} [\Sigma_{s,G' \rightarrow G}(x) \phi_{G'}(x)] dV + \frac{1}{k} \iiint_R \sum_{G'=1}^{N_G} [\chi \nu \Sigma_{f,G' \rightarrow G}(x) \phi_{G'}(x)] dV, \quad x \in R \quad (2)$$

Here, N_G is the number of energy groups and $J_{net,G}$ is the surface-integrated net inward current.

Let us now consider a perturbed problem which contains the same geometry and energy discretization, but with different macroscopic cross sections. We will denote the perturbed cross sections as Σ' , the perturbed scalar flux as ϕ' , and the perturbed neutron current as J' . A multigroup balance equation equivalent to Equation 2 for the perturbed problem can be constructed using Σ' , ϕ' , and J' .

At this point, we will introduce the similarity approximation that is central to the PSP method. We make the assumption that for any given energy group G and any given region R , the scalar flux in the perturbed problem will have the **same spatial distribution** as the scalar flux in the base problem. As such, the perturbed scalar flux can be expressed as the base scalar flux multiplied by some scalar. We call that scalar the “flux ratio”, \mathcal{R}_G^R . We can approximate $\phi'_G(x)$ as $\phi'_G(x) \approx \mathcal{R}_G^R * \phi_G(x), x \in R$. If we divide both sides of the perturbed balance equation by the respective sides of the base balance equation and apply the similarity approximation, we arrive at the following flux ratio equation for energy group G in region R :

$$\frac{\iint\iint_R \Sigma'_{t,G}(x)\phi_G(x)dV}{\iint\iint_R \Sigma_{t,G}(x)\phi_G(x)dV} * \mathcal{R}_G^R = \frac{J'_{net,G} + \sum_{G'=1}^{N_G} \left[\mathcal{R}_{G'}^R \iint\iint_R (\Sigma'_{s,G'\rightarrow G}(x) + \frac{1}{k'} \chi \nu \Sigma'_{f,G'\rightarrow G}(x)) \phi_{G'}(x) dV \right]}{J_{net,G} + \sum_{G'=1}^{N_G} \left[\iint\iint_R (\Sigma_{s,G'\rightarrow G}(x) + \frac{1}{k} \chi \nu \Sigma_{f,G'\rightarrow G}(x)) \phi_{G'}(x) dV \right]} \quad (3)$$

This flux ratio equation is linear with respect to the flux ratios, allowing us to construct a system of linear equations. Most of the terms in this flux ratio equation are either already available to us or very easy to calculate, with the notable exceptions being the perturbed criticality eigenvalue k' and the perturbed net inward current $J'_{net,G}$. These terms must be approximated.

To approximate k' , a standard few-group adjoint-based perturbation theory approach could be employed. However, that approach has yet to be implemented. A simpler “best-case” and “worst-case” approach has been taken in our initial tests. Here we calculate the unrealistic best-case k' with a many-group transport calculation of the perturbed system. The worst-case comes when we assume that the eigenvalue has not changed between the base and perturbed systems (i.e. $k' = k$). This allows us to identify bounds on the effects that choosing an accurate value for k' has on the accuracy of our predictions.

For approximating the perturbed net current, many approaches were tried. After some testing, the approach which provided the most reliably-strong spectrum predictions was a simple closure in which we assume that the partial neutron current is proportional to the flux ratio in the upwind region from which it originates. Therefore, at a given interface between two spatial regions, say region X and region Y , the perturbed partial current at that interface $J'_{X\rightarrow Y,G}$ is approximated to be:

$$J'_{X\rightarrow Y,G} = \mathcal{R}_G^X * J_{X\rightarrow Y,G} = \mathcal{R}_G^X * \iint_{\delta R} \int_{\hat{\Omega} \cdot \hat{n} > 0} (\hat{\Omega} \cdot \hat{n}) * \psi_G(x, \hat{\Omega}) d\hat{\Omega} dS \quad (4)$$

Here, the surface is oriented such that directions for which $\hat{\Omega} \cdot \hat{n} > 0$ are downwind from region X . With this treatment, the overall net inward current for a region R can be found by summing over all of the inward partial currents and subtracting the sum of all the outward partial currents on all of the surfaces bounding the region. If two regions X and Y are not neighboring, then we have $J_{X\rightarrow Y,G} = J_{Y\rightarrow X,G} = 0$.

$$J'_{net,G} = \sum_{R'} \left[\mathcal{R}_G^{R'} * J_{R'\rightarrow R,G} \right] - \mathcal{R}_G^R * \sum_{R'} \left[J_{R\rightarrow R',G} \right] \quad (5)$$

In practice, the assumption that the scalar flux is proportional to the downwind surface flux implicitly assumes that the regions are optically-thick. This could, in theory, limit the applicability of the method compared to a treatment that makes no such assumption.

2.2. Construction of the Linear System

With the derived flux ratio equation, we can write out a system of coupled linear equations. There will be one equation in the system for each energy group and region pair. If there are N_R -many spatial regions and N_G -many energy groups, then the system will contain $(N_R \times N_G)$ -many equations and unknowns. We will begin by defining new variables that allow us to write out the flux ratio equation more concisely. Let us define:

$$J_{out,G}^R \equiv \sum_{R'} [J_{R \rightarrow R',G}] \quad (6)$$

$$S_{G' \rightarrow G}^R \equiv \iiint_R (\Sigma'_{s,G' \rightarrow G}(x) + \frac{1}{k'} \chi \nu \Sigma'_{f,G' \rightarrow G}(x)) \phi_{G'}(x) dV \quad (7)$$

$$Z_G^R \equiv \frac{\iiint_R \Sigma'_{t,G}(x) \phi_G(x) dV}{\iiint_R \Sigma_{t,G}(x) \phi_G(x) dV} * \left(J_{net,G} + \sum_{G'=1}^{N_G} \left[\iiint_R (\Sigma_{s,G' \rightarrow G}(x) + \frac{1}{k} \chi \nu \Sigma_{f,G' \rightarrow G}(x)) \phi_{G'}(x) dV \right] \right) \quad (8)$$

Applying these definitions, applying the surface current treatment found in Equation 5 and rearranging terms allows us to write the flux ratio equation as follows:

$$\sum_{G'=1}^{N_G} [S_{G' \rightarrow G}^R \mathcal{R}_G^R] + \sum_{R'=1}^{N_R} [J_{R' \rightarrow R,G} \mathcal{R}_G^{R'}] - (Z_G^R + J_{out,G}^R) \mathcal{R}_G^R = 0 \quad (9)$$

It can be seen that the $S_{G' \rightarrow G}^R$ terms capture changes in the scattering and fission sources that couple energy groups together within the same region, the $J_{R' \rightarrow R,G}$ terms capture changes in the surface currents that couple neighboring regions together, and the $(Z_G^R + J_{out,G}^R)$ term captures changes in the within-group removal rate and leakage out of the region. It should be noted that this equation is homogeneous when there are no inhomogeneous sources (i.e. sources whose magnitude is independent of the neutron flux) present in the system. In matrix-vector form, the resulting linear system is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \left(\begin{array}{ccc} S_{1 \rightarrow 1}^1 - (J_{out,1}^1 + Z_1^1) & \dots & S_{N_G \rightarrow 1}^1 \\ & \ddots & \\ S_{1 \rightarrow N_G}^1 & \dots & S_{N_G \rightarrow N_G}^1 - (J_{out,N_G}^1 + Z_{N_G}^1) \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{ccc} J_{2 \rightarrow 1,1} & \dots & 0 \\ & \ddots & \\ 0 & \dots & J_{2 \rightarrow 1,N_G} \end{array} \right) & \dots & \left(\begin{array}{ccc} J_{N_R \rightarrow 1,1} & \dots & 0 \\ & \ddots & \\ 0 & \dots & J_{N_R \rightarrow 1,N_G} \end{array} \right) \\ & & \ddots & \\ & \left(\begin{array}{ccc} J_{1 \rightarrow N_R,1} & \dots & 0 \\ & \ddots & \\ 0 & \dots & J_{1 \rightarrow N_R,N_G} \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{ccc} J_{2 \rightarrow N_R,1} & \dots & 0 \\ & \ddots & \\ 0 & \dots & J_{2 \rightarrow N_R,N_G} \end{array} \right) & \dots & \left(\begin{array}{ccc} S_{1 \rightarrow 1}^{N_R} - (J_{out,1}^{N_R} + Z_1^{N_R}) & \dots & S_{N_G \rightarrow 1}^{N_R} \\ & \ddots & \\ S_{1 \rightarrow N_G}^{N_R} & \dots & S_{N_G \rightarrow N_G}^{N_R} - (J_{out,N_G}^{N_R} + Z_{N_G}^{N_R}) \end{array} \right) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{R}_1^1 \\ \mathcal{R}_2^1 \\ \mathcal{R}_3^1 \\ \vdots \\ \mathcal{R}_{N_G}^{N_R} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

By convention, we can express a matrix-vector equation of this form as $Ax = b$. Here A is our square coefficient matrix, x is our vector of flux ratios, and b is our vector of nonhomogeneous neutron sources. In the case where we have no inhomogeneous sources, this reduces to $Ax = 0$.

When the perturbations are set to zero (i.e. $\Sigma' = \Sigma$), the coefficient matrix is rank-deficient by 1, and all of its row sums are analytically zero. In this unperturbed case, the nullspace of A is the 1-dimensional subspace spanned by the vector $[1, 1, \dots, 1]$. Hence, we recover the intuitive solution that, when the cross sections are not perturbed, the flux ratios are all equal to 1.

2.3. Approximate Solution of Ill-Posed Linear System

In general, when the perturbations are non-zero, the PSP coefficient matrix described in the previous section will be full-rank. An important property of full-rank matrices is that their nullspace is identically 0, meaning that $Ax = 0$ can only be exactly satisfied when $x = 0$. Because $x = 0$ is a trivial and unhelpful solution here, this system is inherently **ill-posed** and there are no non-trivial vectors x that will exactly

solve it. We can, however, still solve the system *approximately*. There are many methods by which we can arrive at an approximate solution vector, but the method that was found to give the best prediction accuracy is one based on the singular value decomposition (SVD). The solution method is as follows:

1. Normalize the rows of A such that the diagonal element in each row is equal to -1 . This normalized coefficient matrix is denoted \tilde{A} . This normalization greatly reduces the condition number of the matrix.
2. Perform an SVD on \tilde{A} to find its right singular vectors $[v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{N_R \times N_G}]$ and corresponding singular values $[\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_{N_R \times N_G}]$
3. Take the right singular vector v_{min} corresponding to the smallest singular value σ_{min} as the approximate solution (i.e. take $x = v_i$ where $i = \underset{i \in [1, N_G \times N_R]}{\operatorname{argmin}} (|\sigma_i|)$). This yields an approximate solution

that provably minimizes the 2-norm of the residual $\|\tilde{A}x\|_2$.

After an approximate solution has been reached, the predicted perturbed scalar fluxes are then constructed by multiplying the base scalar flux by the flux ratio of the region and energy group to which it belongs (from the approximate solution vector), $\phi'_{G,pred}(x) = \mathcal{R}_G^R * \phi_G(x)$, $x \in R$. One can then normalize the predicted perturbed fluxes to the desired magnitude.

2.4. Error Metric

In assessing the accuracy of our predicted scalar fluxes, we use a metric that captures both the spatial fidelity and spectral fidelity of the prediction. Nominally, the reason we care about fine spectral information is to preserve reaction rates, so our metric should measure the prediction accuracy of the reaction rates rather than of the flux itself. Additionally, it is beneficial to use a relative error metric rather than an absolute error metric, as this will better allow for comparison of errors across different test problems. We will define our relative reaction rate prediction error as the expression given in Equation 11. Here, the “true” perturbed fluxes $\phi'_G(x)$ come from a many-group transport calculation of the perturbed problem.

$$Error = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{R=1}^{N_R} \sum_{G=1}^{N_G} \left[\iiint_R (\Sigma'_{t,G}(x) (\phi'_{G,pred}(x) - \phi'_G(x)))^2 dV \right]}{\sum_{R=1}^{N_R} \sum_{G=1}^{N_G} \left[\iiint_R (\Sigma'_{t,G}(x) \phi'_G(x))^2 dV \right]}} \quad (11)$$

3. RESULTS

To test the performance of the PSP approach, a series of test problems of varying geometry, material, and spectral properties were constructed. For each test problem, a perturbed problem was constructed by modifying the microscopic cross sections of each isotope while keeping the geometric and isotopic properties of the problem the same. For each isotope in the perturbed problems, a random $\pm 30\%$ perturbation to the scattering, capture, and fission cross sections is applied in each of the 618 fine energy groups present in the nuclear data files.

In each test, an initial transport calculation of the base problem is performed in the neutral particle deterministic transport code PARTISN [5], using the LANL-618 energy group structure. Neutron flux data from that transport calculation are then read from the output files and used to construct the linear PSP system. This system is then solved to find the predicted perturbed spectra, which are then compared to the true perturbed spectra from a subsequent PARTISN calculation of the perturbed problem.

3.1. 1D Bare U233 Sphere (Fast Spectrum)

In this test problem, we look at a bare, critical spatially-uniform sphere of U233 fuel. A diagram of the problem is given in Figure 1. The dashed red lines indicate boundaries for each spatial region. The

relative total cell-wise reaction rate prediction errors are given in Table I. In the best case, we can see that using PSP reduces the prediction error from approximately 4.9% to approximately 1.5%, an $\sim 3\times$ reduction in error. In a spatially-homogeneous problem like this, we can see that introducing additional spatial regions has little impact on the prediction accuracy. Because the flux spectrum will be roughly spatially-uniform, the flux ratios will also be spatially-uniform and additional spatial regions will not provide a noticeable benefit.

Figure 1. Diagrams of Spherical U233 Test Case

Table I. Reaction Rate Prediction Errors for 618-Group U233 Sphere Test Case

Method: \ # of Spatial Regions:	1 Region	2 Regions	4 Regions
PSP (Best-Case, Correct k')	1.493%	1.492%	1.491%
PSP (Worst-Case, $k'=k$)	1.393%	1.408%	1.438%
Without PSP ($\phi'_{pred} = \phi$)	4.921%	4.921%	4.921%

We can note that using the true value for the perturbed criticality eigenvalue k' (as calculated by PARTISN) gives us very slightly decreased prediction accuracy when compared to using the unperturbed criticality eigenvalue k , likely due to some small cancellation of error. One might expect a more pronounced difference in accuracy given the fairly large criticality change of $\Delta k = -1019$ pcm ($k = 1.01169$, $k' = 1.00150$), but that is not what we see here. This is due to the fact that for the purposes of PSP, the criticality eigenvalue is only used to adjust the *relative* magnitudes of the fission and scattering sources. In this problem, the effect of scattering interactions on the neutron spectrum is minimal. The spectral shape is primarily dictated by the absorption cross section and the fission emission spectrum. Because the spectrum is fission-dominated, the change to the relative magnitude of the scattering source from using a different value of k' has only a slight effect on the predicted spectrum.

3.2. 2D Water-Reflected HEU Cylinder (Thermal Spectrum)

In this R-Z problem, we look at a cylinder of HEU surrounded by a light water reflector/moderator. A diagram of the problem is given in Figure 2. The relative total cell-wise reaction rate prediction errors are given in Table II. In the best case, we can see that using PSP reduces the prediction error from approximately 19.5% to approximately 1.7%, an $\sim 11\times$ reduction in error. We can note that using the true value for the perturbed criticality eigenvalue k' gives us noticeably increased prediction accuracy compared to using the unperturbed k in the 4 regions and 8 regions cases. However, using the unperturbed k gives us slightly better accuracy in the 2 regions case, likely due to some cancellation of error effect. In this case, the change in eigenvalue between the base and perturbed problems was $\Delta k = -240$ pcm ($k = 0.97080$, $k' = 0.96840$). Additionally, we can see that using a greater number of spectral regions yields slightly less accurate predictions in this test case. We believe that this is being caused by error introduced in how we calculate the perturbed net neutron currents. When the regions are too small, they are no longer optically thick, and this deviation from the previous assumption degrades prediction accuracy. Ways to mitigate this phenomenon are being investigated.

Figure 2. Diagrams of Cylindrical HEU Test Case

Table II. Reaction Rate Prediction Errors for 618-Group HEU Cylinder Test Case

Method: \ # of Spatial Regions:	2 Regions	4 Regions	8 Regions
PSP (Best-Case, Correct k')	1.667%	1.997%	2.311%
PSP (Worst-Case, $k'=k$)	1.462%	3.544%	3.854%
Without PSP ($\phi'_{pred} = \phi$)	19.54%	19.54%	19.54%

3.3. 2D Be-Reflected Pu Slab (Mixed Spectrum)

In this X-Y slab problem, we look at a slab of Pu metal surrounded by a pure Be-9 reflector. A diagram of the problem is given in Figure 3. The relative total cell-wise reaction rate prediction errors are given in Table III. In the best case, we can see that using PSP reduces the prediction error from approximately 8% to approximately 1.9%, an $\sim 4x$ reduction in error.

Figure 3. Diagrams of 2D Slab Pu Test Case

We can also note that, despite the fairly large change in eigenvalue of $\Delta k = -932$ pcm ($k = 1.05164$, $k' = 1.04232$), using the true value of k' does not have a large effect on the accuracy of our predictions in this case. We believe this is due to the fact that within the beryllium, which composes most of the volume of this problem, the spectrum is dominated by scattering and (n,2n) effects (both of which are described by the scattering source term). Because the scattering source primarily dictates the spectrum shape within most of the problem volume-wise, changes to k' (which manifest as changes in the relative strength of the fission source) have minimal effect. In this test case, we see a situation in which refining our spatial regions gives a significant increase in prediction accuracy. Dividing our problem from 1 region into 4 regions decreases the prediction error by more than a factor of two. This demonstrates the need for multiple spatial regions in situations where there are substantial differences in spectral shape at different points in the problem. In this case, we know that the spectrum within the plutonium region

Table III. Reaction Rate Prediction Errors for 618-Group Plutonium Slab Test Case

Method: \ # of Spatial Regions:	1 Region	4 Regions	16 Regions
PSP (Best-Case, Correct k')	6.735%	2.246%	1.934%
PSP (Worst-Case, $k'=k$)	6.721%	2.221%	1.910 %
Without PSP ($\phi'_{pred} = \phi$)	8.061%	8.061%	8.061%

will be much faster (i.e. higher energy) than in the beryllium region where significant neutron energy loss through downscattering and (n,2n) reactions have occurred.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a novel method called Perturbed Spectrum Prediction (PSP) for predicting, with little computational expense, how the scalar flux distribution in a steady-state problem will change if the cross sections are perturbed. In contrast to other existing methods, PSP requires only a single initial many-group transport solution with no other significant initial computation. PSP can be implemented with standard neutral particle transport solvers, and is generalizable to different types of systems. Using PARTISN as a reference transport solver, a series of tests were performed on problems with varying geometries and spectral characteristics. These tests yielded promising results, showing that PSP can accurately predict how scalar flux distributions change in response to cross section perturbations. Initial results suggest that the PSP methodology is sound and merits further investigation. We believe that this technique may have applications to the construction of accurate group-collapse weighting functions for cross section generation and in efficient predictor-corrector methods for reactor depletion analysis.

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